

THE GROUPS OF PRODUCTS: WHAT THE MEDIA WRITE ABOUT?

№	Groups of products	Country	Sources	URL
1.	Electronics, their components - repurposed for military uses (“dual-use” equipment)	Armenia	Politico: As with Armenia, the government has put in place strict rules on goods like electronics that analysts fear could be stripped down to their components and repurposed for military uses.	https://www.politico.eu/article/russia-ukraine-war-vladimir-putin-trade-partners-sanctions-loopholes-in-face-of-eu-pressure/
2.	Electronic and telecommunications goods (“dual-use” equipment)	Armenia Tako, an Armenian importer	Politico: A draft of the EU’s latest sanctions package, seen by POLITICO, shows Brussels is planning to follow suit and impose tighter trade restrictions on at least one of those companies — Tako, an Armenian importer of electronic and telecommunications goods already sanctioned by the U.S.	https://www.politico.eu/article/russia-ukraine-war-vladimir-putin-trade-partners-sanctions-loopholes-in-face-of-eu-pressure/
3-5.	Thermal imaging cameras, night vision scopes Thermal imaging camera & their components (spare parts) such as gas turbine engines	«2022 from various countries, ranging from China to Serbia to Myanmar»	Politico: The Russian state-owned company Rosoboronexport has been importing microchips, thermal imagers, and spare parts such as gas turbine engines since 2022 from various countries, ranging from China to Serbia to Myanmar»	https://www.lrt.lt/en/news-in-english/19/2017444/vilnius-based-company-s-equipment-falls-into-russian-snipers-hands-lrt-investigation https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html
6.	Microcircuits for rockets		24TV/Ukraine	https://24tv.ua/business/desyatki-kompaniyi-yevropi-dopomagayut-rosiyskiy-armiyi-nazvi_n2316435
7.	Sleeves		24TV/Ukraine	https://24tv.ua/business/desyatki-kompaniyi-yevropi-dopomagayut-rosiyskiy-armiyi-nazvi_n2316435

	Armament		CNN: In addition to supplying drones, Beijing may also consider transferring ammunition, primarily for small arms rather than artillery.	https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-rozglyadaye-postachannya-rosiji-artileriji-ostanni-novini-50306756.html
8.	Engines for warships		24TV/Ukraine	https://24tv.ua/business/desyatki-kompaniyi-yevropi-dopomagayut-rosiyskiy-armiyi-nazvi_n2316435
9.	Body armors	China North Industries Group Corporation Limited (one of the largest state defense contractors in the PRC) / China , in late 2022, routed via Turkey routed via Turkey, some via UAE , December 2022	24TV/Ukraine Politico&ImportG enius, a customs data aggregator. 16.03.2022: 1,000 assault rifles and over 12 tons of Chinese body armor and 12 shipments of drone parts (recipient: Russian company Techkrim) more than 800 tons of body armors worth \$10 million produced by a Turkish company Ariteks	https://24tv.ua/business/desyatki-kompaniyi-yevropi-dopomagayut-rosiyskiy-armiyi-nazvi_n2316435 https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html https://www.politico.eu/article/chinese-companies-are-shipping-rifles-body-armor-to-russia/
	over 800 body armors			https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html
	Body armors	Chinese company Xinxing Guangzhou Import & Export Co	Politico&ImportG enius, a customs data aggregator. 16.03.2022: The shipments took place between June and December 2022	https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html https://www.politico.eu/article/chinese-companies-are-shipping-rifles-body-armor-to-russia/
10.	Shoes for the military of the Russian Federation drones and ammunition	China	24TV/Ukraine CNN: The US has intelligence that the Chinese government is considering providing Russia with drones and ammunition for use in the war in Ukraine, three sources familiar with the	https://24tv.ua/business/desyatki-kompaniyi-yevropi-dopomagayut-rosiyskiy-armiyi-nazvi_n2316435 https://edition.cnn.com/2023/02/24/politics/us-intelligence-china-drones-russia-ukraine/index.html

	3500drones	Finland	intelligence told CNN. Ukrinform	<i>Finnish customs suspects two companies of sending almost 3,500 drones to Russia. /</i> Ukrinform.05.12.2023. https://www.ukrinform.net/rubric-crime/3796099-finnish-customs-suspects-two-companies-of-sending-almost-3500-drones-to-russia.html
11.	1,000 assault rifles and other equipment that could be used for military purposes, including drone parts and body armor (according to trade and customs data obtained by POLITICO)	China North Industries Group Corporation Limited (one of the largest state defense contractors in the PRC) / China, 2022	Politico&ImportGenius, a customs data aggregator. 16.03.2022: 1,000 assault rifles and other equipment. Recipient: a Russian company called Tekhkrim that also does business with the Russian state and military The shipments took place between June and December 2022, according to the data provided by ImportGenius, a customs data aggregator. The CQ-A rifles, modeled off of the M16 but tagged as “civilian hunting rifles” in the data, have been reported to be in use by paramilitary police in China and by armed forces from the Philippines to South Sudan and Paraguay.	https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html https://www.politico.eu/article/chinese-companies-are-shipping-rifles-body-armor-to-russia/

12.	<p>Drone parts (12 batches of drone parts)</p> <p>Components for drones (Chinese drone Mugin-5)</p> <p>Attack drones</p>	<p>China North Industries Group Corporation Limited (one of the largest state defense contractors in the PRC) / China, 2022 routed via Turkey</p> <p>Chinese company Da-Jiang Innovations Science & Technology Co (DJI) (is under US sanctions), November-December 2022</p> <p>China, 2023</p>	<p>Politico&ImportG enius, a customs data aggregator. 16.03.2022: 1,000 assault rifles and other equipment, body armors and drone parts (12 batches of drone parts). Recipient: a Russian company called Tekhkrim that also does business with the Russian state and military: The shipments took place between June and December 2022</p> <p>Mugin Limited condemns the use of its products during times of war. Some technical bloggers refer to the Mugin-5 as "Alibaba drones" because they could be purchased for as low as \$15,000 on Chinese websites, including Alibaba and Taobao.</p> <p>Der Spiegel (Germany), 25.02.23& Russia is likely in negotiations with the Chinese company Xi'an Bingo Intelligent Aviation Technology to purchase 100 strike drones. The batch could potentially be delivered as early as spring.</p> <p>The German publication Der Spiegel first reported that China may provide attack drones to Russia.</p> <p>CNN: The US has intelligence that</p>	<p>https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html</p> <p>https://www.politico.eu/article/chinese-companies-are-shipping-rifles-body-armor-to-russia/</p> <p>https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html</p> <p>https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/mugin-5-ukrajina-zbila-kitayskiy-dron-bilya-slov-yanska-cnn-novini-ukrajini-50311024.html</p> <p>https://edition.cnn.com/2023/02/24/politics/us-intelligence-china-drones-russia-ukraine/index.html</p> <p>https://www.wsj.com/articles/china-12-point-peace-plan-russia-ukraine-vladimir-putin-annalena-baerbock-55049d99</p> <p>https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-rozglyadaye-postachannya-rosiji-artileriji-ostanni-novini-50306756.html</p> <p>https://edition.cnn.com/2023/02/24/politics/us-intelligence-china-drones-russia-ukraine/index.html</p>
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			<p>the Chinese government is considering providing Russia with drones and ammunition for use in the war in Ukraine, three sources familiar with the intelligence told CNN.</p> <p>Since invading Ukraine, Russia has repeatedly requested drones and ammunition from China, the sources familiar with the intelligence said, and Chinese leadership has been actively debating over the last several months whether or not to send the lethal aid, the sources added.</p> <p>US intelligence officials have collected information in recent weeks, however, that suggests China is now leaning towards providing the equipment. The US and its allies last week began publicly warning about China's potential military support to Russia in an effort to deter Beijing from moving ahead with it and crossing a point of no return in terms of being seen as a pariah on the world stage, US officials said.</p>	
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12.1	Attack drones		Ukrainian official media BLYSKAVKA (ukr.Блискавка): 'Russia is amassing forces for a strike on the energy infrastructure' - military expert Sergey 'Flash'"	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uFzUD2tQrXU 02:19 minutes. 'Lancets' were found with American-made components - do sanctions not work? 02:41 minutes. Shelling of Ukraine with 'cheap drones' - Russian developments or assistance from China? Quote: "Sanctions are effective only where specific military technologies and military developments are applied. If these are some microchips or commercial components, what we call 'consumer goods,' - they can be bought in any country in the world. In this case, sanctions will be less effective."
13.	navigation equipment, satellite imagery, vehicle components and other raw materials	China, 2023	Politico : China ships assault weapons and body armor	https://www.politico.eu/article/chinese-companies-are-shipping-rifles-body-armor-to-russia/
14.	“dual-use” equipment	China, 2023	Politico : Although the customs data does not show that Beijing is selling a large amount of weapons to Moscow specifically to aid its war effort, it reveals that China is supplying Russian companies with previously unreported “dual-use” equipment — commercial items that could also be used on the battlefield in Ukraine.	https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html https://www.politico.eu/article/chinese-companies-are-shipping-rifles-body-armor-to-russia/
15.	Satellite images	China, 2023	In the United States, it has been stated that a Chinese company provided satellite images to the Wagner Private Military Company (PMC). CNN : The provision of drones and ammunition – which would likely be for small arms like handheld weaponry rather than larger artillery, the sources said – would mark a	https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html

			<p>significant escalation of China's support for Russia, which to date has been largely limited to Chinese companies providing non-lethal equipment like helmets, flak jackets, and satellite imagery to Russian forces.</p> <p>The U.S. Department of the Treasury has stated that Spacety China provided satellite images of Ukraine, captured using synthetic aperture radar technology, to the Russian technology company Terra-Tech. These images were intended to assist the Wagner Private Military Company (PMC).</p> <p>Feb 28 (Reuters): China's blacklisted Spacety allegedly shared satellite images with Russia's Wagner group-U.S. official. Chinese satellite firm Spacety, which was added to a U.S. trade blacklist earlier this month, provided satellite images to Russian mercenary company Wagner Group, a Biden administration official said on Tuesday.</p>	<p>https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/v-ssha-zayavilichto-kitayskaya-kompaniya-peredavala-chvk-vagnera-sputnikovye-snimki-50307455.html</p> <p>https://www.reuters.com/article/usa-china-tech/chinas-blacklisted-spacety-allegedly-shared-satellite-images-with-russias-wagner-group-u-s-official-idUKL1N3581PC</p>
16.	Microchips	China via Serbia and Myanmar	Politico	<p>https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postaviv-rosiji-gvintivki-ta-bronezhileti-zmi-ostanni-novini-50311256.html</p> <p>Politico: "Since 2022, the Russian state-owned company Rosoboronexport has been importing microchips, thermal imagers, and components like gas turbine engines from various countries, ranging from China to Serbia and Myanmar"</p>

				Die Geschäfte laufen nach ähnlichem Muster ab. Ein im Westen ansässiges Unternehmen verkauft Produkte an einen Konzern in einem Drittstaat, der sie weiter an russische Händler vertreibt. Neben Kasachstan und Armenien sind es Georgien, die Vereinigten Arabischen Emirate und das Nato-Mitglied Türkei, die dabei eine zentrale Rolle spielen.
19.	Ölförderung	Saudi-Arabien	Die Welt	<p>https://www.welt.de/wirtschaft/energie/plus244638974/Benzin-Heizuel-und-Co-Opec-drosselt-Foerderung-zum-Vorteil-Russlands-zum-Nachteil-der-Verbraucher.html</p> <p>Opec drosselt Ölförderung – zum Vorteil Russlands, zum Nachteil der Verbraucher. Das Ölkartell Opec („Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries“)</p> <p>Das einflussreichste Opec-Mitglied Saudi-Arabien kürzt mit weiteren Förderländern die Produktion ab Mai um 1,15 Millionen Barrel</p>
20.	drones and weapons technology	Deutschland via Kazakhstan, Armenia, Georgia, the United Arab Emirates	Die Welt SANKTIONEN „Deutschland steht an der Spitze des westlichen Schattenhandels mit Russland“ Veröffentlicht am 19.06.2023 Von Carolina Drüten, Christine Kensch, Philip Volkmann-Schluck	<p>Drüten, K., Kensch, Ch., Volkmann-Schluck, Ph. <i>Deutschland steht an der Spitze des westlichen Schattenhandels mit Russland.</i> Die Welt. Sanktionen. 19.06.2023.</p> <p>https://www.welt.de/politik/ausland/plus245910740/Sanktionen-Deutschland-steht-an-der-Spitze-des-westlichen-Schattenhandels-mit-Russland.html</p>
21	Geld&		die WELT (die tschechische Denkfabrik Datlab)	<p>https://www.welt.de/wirtschaft/plus245841826/Putin-Hier-machen-russische-Oligarchen-immer-noch-gute-Geschaeft.html</p> <p>2,5 Milliarden Euro flossen demnach an die Firmen. Und ein Teil davon weiter an Vertraute Putins.</p>
22.	Indications of political dependence on Russia	Austria	die WELT Ein Land in Putins Ketten. Von Matthew Karnitschnig Veröffentlicht am 05.06.2023	<p>https://www.welt.de/politik/ausland/plus245690398/Oesterreich-Ein-Land-in-Putins-Ketten.html</p>
23.	certain automotive parts	Export from Bulgaria to Turkey, the United Arab Emirates, Kazakhstan	Customs Compliance & Risk Management (CCRM) Journal , Issue 23, October / November 2023	<p>https://www.customsclearance.net/en/articles/non-tariff-measures-or-non-tariff-barriers-eu-sanctions-against-russia-and-belarus</p> <p>export of certain automotive parts of HS Chapters 84 and 85 to Turkey, the United Arab Emirates, Kazakhstan and others.</p>

24.	military equipment (dual-use technologies and non-lethal assistance, such as helmets and body armor)	China	<p>The New Voice of Ukraine: Французькі чиновники повідомили CNN, що Бонне мав на увазі як технології подвійного призначення, так і нелетальну допомогу, таку як шоломи та бронезилети</p> <p>CNN: Emmanuel Bonne, an adviser to French President Emmanuel Macron, made the claim at the Aspen Security Forum while speaking to CNN's Jim Sciutto</p>	<p>“У Макрона заявили, що Китай постачає Росії військове обладнання для війни проти України”. New Voice. 21 липня 2023 https://nv.ua/ukr/world/geopolitics/kitay-postachaye-rosiji-viyskove-obladnannya-dlya-viyni-proti-ukrajini-radnik-makrona-ostanninovini-50340626.html</p> <p>“Top French foreign policy adviser claims China is delivering military equipment to support Russia” From CNN's Jim Sciutto and Rashard Rose, July 20, 2023 https://edition.cnn.com/europe/live-news/russia-ukraine-war-news-07-20-23/h_5f0322bd1c12c7588b1267efaeb5088b</p>
25.	enrichment of uranium to near weapons-grade	Iran	<p>The New Voice of Ukraine</p> <p>Reuters</p>	<p>“Іран знову нарощує виробництво високозбагаченого урану”, The New Voice of Ukraine /Євген Василенко. 26 грудня 2023 https://nv.ua/ukr/world/countries/iran-naroshchuyevirobnictvo-visokozbagachenogo-uranu-50379516.html</p> <p>“Iran undoes slowdown in enrichment of uranium to near weapons-grade –IAEA”, Reuters/ Francois Murphy. December 26, 2023 https://www.reuters.com/world/middle-east/iran-undoes-slowdown-enrichment-uranium-near-weapons-grade-iaea-2023-12-26/</p>
26.	dual-use microelectronics = sensitive technology: military-grade equipment			<p>Today, the Justice Department unsealed an indictment charging Iranian national Hossein Hatefi Ardakani and co-defendant Gary Lam, who worked for a Chinese company, with crimes related to the procurement of U.S.-manufactured dual-use microelectronics for the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps (IRGC) Aerospace Force Self Sufficiency Jihad Organization’s (ASF SSJO) one-way attack unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) program.</p>
27.	+used foreign bank accounts to funnel money from the Russian customers to KanRus Trading in the US	U.S. from US to Russia via third countries Armenia, Cyprus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz Republic, the United Arab Emirates	Office of Public Affairs. U.S. Department of Justice.	<p>Owner of Kansas Company Pleads Guilty to Crimes Related to Scheme to illegally Export U.S. Avionics Equipment to Russia and Russian End Users. Press Release. Office of Public Affairs. U.S. Department of Justice. 19.12.2023 https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/owner-kansas-company-pleads-guilty-crimes-related-scheme-illegally-export-us-avionics accessed 21.12.2023; https://lnkd.in/dSn4TrbJ</p>

28.	used Scania and Volvo trucks	Finland	русскоязычная Служба новостей Yle (Финляндия) (in Russian)	<i>После начала войны финская компания экспортировала в Россию запчастей для грузовых автомобилей на миллионы евро.</i> Служба новостей Yle (Финляндия). 26.11.2023. Снято 26.12.2023. https://yle.fi/a/74-20062208 (in Russian) (бывшие в употреблении грузовики Scania и Volvo: поставщик в РФ финская компания Idän Liikenteenvälitys IL)
29.	+ spare prts for trucks Scania and Volvo	China, Hong Kong, Taiwan via Finland	русскоязычная Служба новостей Yle (Финляндия) (in Russian)	<i>После начала войны финская компания экспортировала в Россию запчастей для грузовых автомобилей на миллионы евро.</i> Служба новостей Yle (Финляндия). 26.11.2023. Снято 26.12.2023. https://yle.fi/a/74-20062208 (in Russian) (запчасти к грузовикам Scania и Volvo; финская фирма HD-Parts – может быть крупнейшим поставщиком запчастей к грузовикам во всем западном мире)
30.	tugboats	Finland	Ukrinform	<i>Finnish customs suspects two companies of sending almost 3,500 drones to Russia.</i> / Ukrinform.05.12.2023. https://www.ukrinform.net/rubric-crime/3796099-finnish-customs-suspects-two-companies-of-sending-almost-3500-drones-to-russia.html
31.	oil (profit in Russia!)	From Russia to&via India to EU, United States (US), United Kingdom (UK), Japan, Canada, Australia and via UAE to US, UK, Japan, EU, Canada; via Singapore to US, UK, Japan, EU, Australia; via Turkey to US, EU, Canada	UK Independent	Sharma, Shweta. <i>Europe buying Russian oil via India at record rates in 2023 despite Ukraine war.</i> Independent. 12.01.2024. Скачано 15.01.24. https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/europe/russia-oil-europe-india-ukraine-war-b2477443.html « India is benefiting from importing cut-price Russian oil amid European sanctions – and also selling that same oil to EU markets at full price once it has been refined»
32.	sensors, diesel engines, fuel pumps and transmission equipment;	Finland and via Uzbekistan	русскоязычная Служба новостей Yle (Финляндия) (in Russian)	<i>Yle: более 20 финских компаний экспортируют в Россию товары военного назначения.</i> Yle News. 15 января 2024. https://meduza.io/news/2024/01/15/yle-bolee-20-finskih-kompaniy-eksportiruyut-v-rossiyu-tovary-voennogo-naznacheniya (in Russian)

	equipment for military research, product development and intelligence : signal analysis equipment, frequency synthesizer, printed circuit board parts, optical devices and volt meters.			«датчики, дизельные двигатели, топливные насосы и трансмиссионное оборудование»; «оборудование для военных исследований, разработки продуктов и разведки»...: «оборудование для анализа сигналов, синтезаторы частот, детали для печатных плат, оптические устройства и вольтметры» (in Russian).
33.	rockets made by North Korea	North Korea	Ukrainian official media BLYSKAVKA (in Ukrainian)	<i>Офіс Генпрокурора отримав перші докази того, що росія запускала по Україні ракети, виготовлені Північною Кореєю.</i> Офіс Генпрокурора. Ukrainian official media BLYSKAVKA. 15.01.2024. https://cutt.ly/Blyskavka (in Ukrainian)
34.	a Dassault Falcon 7X aircraft	Kazakhstan	Eurasianet & Verstka (Jan 5, 2024) & News website Vlast.kz <i>Instrument: some suspicious irregularities over tax payments</i>	<i>Kumenov, Almaz. Kazakhstan: Alleged Deripaska plane purchase raises sanctions bypass questions.</i> Eurasianet. Jan 8, 2024 https://eurasianet.org/kazakhstan-alleged-deripaska-plane-purchase-raises-sanctions-bypass-questions “Russian billionaire Oleg Deripaska is alleged to have bought a Dassault Falcon 7X aircraft, similar to but not the one pictured, from Kazakhstan-based Irtysh Air”. “Verstka claimed in a report published on Jan 5 that the Dassault Falcon 7X aircraft was bought for around \$36 million from Irtysh Air in February 2023. The outlet said its reporting was based on scrutiny of Russian customs data and an analysis of Deripaska’s movements over the past year.” “News website Vlast.kz said it had not received any response to queries over the possibility that the airline had bought the aircraft in question and immediately resold it without going through the motions of registering it in Kazakhstan.” “Digging into Irtysh Air, Vlast.kz detected some apparently suspicious irregularities over its tax payments , despite the fact that the company does not offer regular flights. While the company paid the equivalent of around \$5,000 in taxes in 2022, its bills to the tax service in 2023 — the year of the alleged jet sale — amounted to around \$66,000.”
35.	Components for Kh-32 cruise missiles		RBC-Ukraine	https://newsukraine.rbc.ua/news/guerrillas-find-out-how-many-x-32-cruise-1710836951.html Guerrillas find out how many Kh-32 cruise missiles Russia plans to produce within year

36.	42 new parts for Russian X-59 aircraft missiles, together with "Shahed" UAVs		Site of the National Agency on Corruption Prevention, Ukraine 05.01.2024 Unified Database of Foreign Components in Weapons	NACP has supplemented the database of foreign components in weapons with parts of Russian X-59 aircraft missiles. Site of the National Agency on Corruption Prevention. https://nazk.gov.ua/en/news/nacp-has-supplemented-the-database-of-foreign-components-in-weapons-with-parts-of-russian-x-59-aircraft-missiles/
37.	2k foreign components found in Russian and Iranian weapons; components used by Russia and Iran in various types of UAVs, missiles, electronic warfare systems and many other types of weapons and military equipment		Site of the National Agency on Corruption Prevention, Ukraine 7.12.2023	The NACP launches the world's first open database with over 2k foreign components found in Russian and Iranian weapons. Site of the National Agency on Corruption Prevention https://nazk.gov.ua/en/news/the-nacp-launches-the-world-s-first-open-database-with-over-2k-foreign-components-found-in-russian-and-iranian-weapons/
38.	chips, semiconductors and other technology embedded in missiles and other military products	from USA to russia via Georgia, Kazakhstan and Turkey	Capital news service, USA	Wilson, Katharine. US components still found in Russian weapons against Ukraine, experts tell Congress. Capital news service. URL: https://cnsmaryland.org/2024/02/27/us-components-still-found-in-russian-weapons-against-ukraine-experts-tell-congress/
39.	Czech engines, American electronics	Czech Republic, USA	Newspaper «Економічна правда», Ukraine	Чеські двигуни, американська електроніка. Як дрон «Ланцет» викриває дірки в антиросійських санкціях. Економічна правда. [Czech engines, American electronics. How the Lancet drone exposes holes in anti-Russian sanctions. Economic truth.] https://www.epravda.com.ua/publications/2023/08/28/703621/
40.	automotive parts	from Bulgaria via Turkey, the United Arab Emirates, Kazakhstan and others	Customs Compliance & Risk Management (CCRM) Journal	Peycheva, B. (2023). EU sanctions against RU and BY: non-tariff measures or non-tariff barriers? Customs Compliance & Risk Management (CCRM) Journal, Issue 23, October / November 2023 https://www.customsclearance.net/en/articles/non-tariff-measures-or-non-tariff-barriers-eu-sanctions-against-russia-and-belarus

41.	338 Lapua Magnum cartridge for Orsis T-5000 screw guns	USA manufacturer American company <i>Hornady</i>	<p>24tv.ua</p> <p>Politico</p>	<p>Сиваківський, Я. (2023). «Хакнули систему»: російська компанія під санкціями змогла купити сотні тисяч патронів з Америки. https://24tv.ua/business/rosiyani-zmogli-kupiti-100-tisyach-amerikanskih-patroniv_n2337621</p> <p>Panov, S., Sarah Anne Aarup, S. Anne & Busvine, D. (2023). How US-made sniper ammunition ends up in Russian rifles. Politico. https://www.politico.eu/article/how-us-made-sniper-ammunition-russia-rifles-weapon-ukraine-war/ Accessed June 19, 2023</p>
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